

A Method for the Analysis of Aluminium- and Potassium-rich Silicate Rocks by X-Ray Fluorescence Spectrometry using Synthetic Calibration Standards

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X-Ray fluorescence (XRF) spectrometry has been widely used in the analysis of geological rock samples for their major and trace elemental composition. Standards covering the range as expected in the unknown samples are essential to get reliable data for major and trace element composition of unknown rock samples. A wide range of international rock standards is available for analysing most of the rock types ranging from felsic to mafic composition¹. However, such rock standards are not available for some rocks with unusual composition. In these cases it becomes necessary to prepare synthetic standards bracketing the expected compositional range in samples to be analysed. Present work is a discussion on the data obtained on the synthetic standards prepared for analysing some rocks which are high in both alumina and alkalis (especially K₂O) for which no comparable natural rock standard is available. These rocks of unusual compositions are chiefly composed of minerals like kyanite and sericite of varying amounts, suggesting that their Al₂O₃ may range between 20 and 40% and K₂O between 1 and 12%.

Results and Discussion

The correlation coefficients (*r*) between the weight percentages of various oxides in the synthetic standards prepared and the intensities obtained for the oxides are >0.99 for all the elements. This suggests that the regression of the intensities obtained for unknown samples using the above mentioned calibration curves can give very good results for most oxides.

The precision and accuracy of the data, which can be obtained using these calibration curves have been quantified. The precision which is the measure of the repeatability of an analytical measurement^{2,3} is affected by (i) errors in sampling, (ii) contamination during sample preparation, (iii) instrumental drift and (iv) counting statistics. Results of replicate analysis of a monitor standard shows that the coefficients of variation of all the elements analysed vary between 0.24 and 5.98. Ragland² suggested that for a good precision, the coefficient of variations should be <3-4 for all oxides, and for SiO₂ it should be <2. The coefficients of variation for important constituents, viz. SiO₂, Al₂O₃, TiO₂, CaO and K₂O are <2 in the standards we analysed. In all these cases coefficients of variation are <3 excepting for those of MnO and MgO which have

been taken in very minor quantities. The low intensities corresponding to these minor oxides may be responsible for higher coefficients of variation. The results presented show that for most oxides the precision is very good.

The accuracy is the measure of the closeness between the obtained values and expected values of the international reference samples analysed as unknown samples^{2,3}. Following Ragland², accuracy has been estimated using the Chi-square method. The estimation of accuracies using the data obtained on the international reference samples (GSJ granodiorite standard-JG-1A and Russian granite standard-CR-1A) are presented in Table 1. The acceptable range of χ^2 which is the summation of the deviations from the expected value is <0.1-0.15 (Ragland²). It may be observed that the χ^2 value (sum of deviations of 8 oxides) in the case of JG-1A standard is only 0.13 and it is slightly higher (0.21) in the case of CR-1A. In case of CR-1A the higher χ^2 is due to deviation in SiO₂. In addition, we have estimated the accuracy for only SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ contents in the B-69 (NBS bauxite standard), CR-1A, CT-1A (Russian granite and basalt standards respectively), JG-1A (GSJ granodiorite standard) and SY-3 (Canadian syenite standard) international reference standards. These results are also presented in Table 1. It may be noticed that the χ^2 values in these standards fall in the range 0.005-0.069. These results show that the accuracy and precision obtained while analysing rocks with unusual compositions using synthetic standards fall in the acceptable range.

We have also analysed for K₂O contents in rock samples of the present study by atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS) using the following natural rock standards: CT-1A, CR-1A, JF-1, JF-2, JG-1A, granite standards of Geological Survey of Finland (RS-81 and RS-111), GH (French granite standard); and GSR-5 (Chinese shale standard). The data obtained on K₂O by AAS method are in good agreement with the data obtained using XRF technique. The average coefficient of variation for 12 samples between the data obtained by the two methods is only 1.29 and the coefficients of variation are in the range 0.35-3.30.

Thus, while not compromising on the accuracy of the data we have been able to achieve greater freedom of selection of range of compositions by using synthetic standards in the analysis of natural rock samples with un-

NOTE

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF ACCURACY USING THE DATA OBTAINED ON SOME INTERNATIONAL ROCK STANDARDS ANALYSED AS UNKNOWN SAMPLES BY CHI-SQUARED METHOD*

	JG-1A				CR-1A			
	OV	EV	c	p	OV	EV	c	p
SiO ₂	73.320	72.190	0.018	1.566	75.048	72.360	0.100	3.714
Al ₂ O ₃	15.209	14.220	0.069	6.958	14.809	13.840	0.068	7.000
TiO ₂	0.220	0.250	0.004	-12.000	0.060	0.070	0.001	-14.286
Fe ₂ O ₃	1.974	2.050	0.003	-3.712	2.161	2.190	0.000	-1.330
MnO	0.080	0.060	0.007	33.333	0.230	0.195	0.006	17.949
MgO	0.740	0.690	0.004	7.246	0.460	0.540	0.012	-14.815
CaO	1.954	2.130	0.015	-8.265	0.220	0.190	0.005	15.789
K ₂ O	4.201	4.010	0.009	4.751	4.398	4.140	0.016	6.230
χ^2			0.127				0.208	

	SiO ₂				Al ₂ O ₃				
	OV	EV	c	p	OV	EV	c	p	χ^2
B-69	13.450	13.410	0.0001	0.299	49.290	48.750	0.006	1.943	0.006
CR-1A	73.798	73.360	0.0025	0.585	14.010	13.840	0.002	1.231	0.005
JG-1A	73.813	72.190	0.036	2.248	14.557	14.220	0.008	2.370	0.045
SY-3	60.763	59.680	0.020	1.815	11.142	11.760	0.032	-5.257	0.052
CT1A	50.085	49.130	0.019	1.943	13.382	14.230	0.051	-5.961	0.069

*OV = Obtained value; EV = expected value; $c = (OV-EV)^2/EV$; $p = [(OV-EV)/EV] \times 100$ (percent deviation); $\chi^2 = \Sigma [(OV-EV)^2/EV]$.

TABLE 2—INSTRUMENTAL PARAMETERS FOR XRF ANALYSIS

Element	Collimator	Crystal	Voltage kV	Current mA	2 θ angle of goniometer	Background (angle)
Si	Coarse	PET	40	30	109.80	+1.40
Al	Coarse	TlAP	40	30	38.40	+1.10
Ti	Fine	LiF 200	45	30	86.65	-0.70
Fe	Fine	LiF 220	50	30	86.15	+2.20
Ca	Fine	LiF 200	40	30	113.45	+1.60
Mg	Coarse	TlAP	40	30	45.68	+0.70
Na	Coarse	TlAP	40	30	55.55	+1.10
K	Coarse	LiF 200	40	30	137.18	+1.00
Mn	Fine	LiF 200	45	30	63.60	-0.70

usual compositions. The results obtained during the course of analysis show that reliable data can be obtained using synthetic standards.

Experimental

Specpure SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MgO, MnO, CaCO₃, NaCl and KCl were used for preparing the synthetic standards. The pure chemicals were dried at 300° in an oven and weighed to an accuracy in the fifth decimal place using a Metler balance and ten synthetic standards were prepared to cover the expected compositional range in the samples to be analysed. The major constituents, viz. SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and K₂O are taken to vary from 45 to 79, 13 to 43 and 2 to 7 weight percent respectively.

The powders of synthetic standards, rock samples and international reference samples (JG-1A-GSJ granodiorite and CR-1A-Russian granite) were mixed thoroughly in an agate mortar along with flux consisting lithium tetraborate, lithium metaborate and lanthanum oxide in the ratio of 6 : 3 : 1. Lanthanum oxide was used as a heavy absorber to minimise the matrix effects. Sample-to-flux ratio was kept at 1 : 4. The sample-flux mixtures were fused for 30 min in 5% gold-platinum crucibles at 1200° using a Herzog auto-

matic fusion machine. The analysis of all the beads (except for Na which would be affected by La of the flux⁴) was performed in the same run by XRF spectrometry.

The analysis was performed using an on-line AT-386 PC attached to a Philips PW 1400 microprocessor controlled sequential X-ray fluorescence spectrometer with 100 kV X-ray generator and 72 position automatic sample changer. Different peak as well as background counts were measured for the elements. Instrumental parameters used during the analysis are given in Table 2. A detailed discussion of instrumental parameters and operating conditions of XRF is the same as reported earlier⁵.

STD 5 (synthetic standard No. 5) was used as monitor and was analysed 9 times to estimate the instrumental precision. The intensities obtained for various elements in other synthetic standards were normalised with the intensities obtained on the monitor standard to avoid effects of instrumental drifts during the analysis.

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